

THE INSCRIPTIONS OF DHĀR AND MĀNDŪ.

BY
ZAFAR HASAN, B.A.

INTRODUCTION.

(A SHORT HISTORY OF MĀLWA.)

The history of Mālwa up to the beginning of the British supremacy in India may conveniently be divided into five periods:—

- (1) The pre-Mohamedan period.
- (2) The rule of the governors under the Sultāns of Delhi, 705-804 H. (1305—1401 A.D.)
- (3) The rule of the independent (Ghori and Khilji) kings, 804-937 H. (1401-1530 A.D.).
- (4) The period from the end of the rule of Khilji kings to the final conquest of Mālwa by the Emperor Akbar.
- (5) Mālwa as a province of the Mogul empire.

The information available for the pre-Mohamedan period has been put together by Captain Luard in the Dhār State Gazetteer (pp. 7-8 and 128 seq.); as I am concerned with the Mohamedan period only, it is sufficient for me here to refer to the Gazetteer.

It is not known when this province was first conquered by the Mohamedans.¹ Most probably Quṭbuddin Aibak reduced also Mālwa when he directed his expedition against Naharwālā² (Gujarāt). But it is almost certain that the Mohamedans could not hold it,³ till its final conquest was effected by Āinul-Mulk Multānī, a general of Ālāuddin Khilji in the year 705 (1305 A.D.).⁴ This Āinul-Mulk was appointed the first governor of the newly conquered province. After him there came other governors all appointed by the Delhi emperors, and this system went on for nearly a century (705-804 A.H. 1305-1401 A.D.)

About the year 792 (1359 A.D.) one Dilāwar Khān⁵ was sent from Delhi as a governor of the province. After the death of Firoz Shāh 790 (1388 A.D.) the power of the Delhi

¹ The inscription on the tomb of Abdullah Shāh Chāngāl (see above, pp. 2-3) gives only a traditional account of the first conquest of Mālwa by the Mohamedans.

² Briggs' *Ferishta*, Vol. I. p. 197. *Ferishta*, Persian text (ed. Lucknow 1321-3 H) part I. p. 62.

³ *Ferishta* contradicts his own statement, viz. "In the year 664, he (Gheias-ood-Din Bulban) was advised by his council to undertake an expedition to reduce the kingdoms of Guzerat and Malwa, which had been annexed to the empire by Kootb-ood-Deen Eibak, but had since shaken the Mohamedan yoke. To this measure he by no means assented." (*Briggs' Ferishta*, Vol. I, p. 255, *Ferishta*, Persian text, part I, p. 77) when he says (*Briggs' Ferishta*, Vol. IV, p. 168, *Ferishta*, Persian text, part II, p. 234) that Mālwa was under the kings of Delhi from the rule of Ghiyāthuddin till the death of Maḥmūd Tughlaq, the son of Firoz Shāh. The dates 710 and 789 are not found in the Persian original and have been wrongly added by Briggs.

⁴ *Tārīkh Alāi*, *Elliot's History of India*, Vol. III, p. 76; E. Barnes (*Dhār and Mandu*, p. 3) regards the conquest of Mālwa by Āinul-Mulk Multānī to have been the first invasion of the Mohamedans into the province.

⁵ The real name of Dilāwar Khān was Husain. He was a descendant on his mother's side of Shihābuddin Ghori (Briggs reading Shām for Sām adds "of Damascus"). His grandfather came from Ghor and held high office under the Delhi government. His father was enrolled among the nobility and received a title. Dilāwar Khān also attained a very high rank in the reign of Firoz Shāh Tughlaq. *Briggs' Ferishta*, Vol. IV, pp. 168-70. *Ferishta*, Persian text, part II, p. 234. Dilāwar Khān and Muḥaffar Shāh of Gujarāt were together in the service of Firoz Shāh. See *Local Mohamedan dynasties*, Gujarat by Bayley, p. 84 n. Jahāngir (*Tuzuk-i-Jahāngir* Persian text, p. 201) calls him 'Amid Shāh Ghori, and this title is also given him in inscriptions II and III.

kings was much reduced, and the ruin caused by Timūr's invasion brought it to its lowest point. Still Mālwa acknowledged its allegiance to the central power, as Dilāwar Khān treated Maḥmūd Tughlaq, the emperor of Delhi as his superior, when the latter was obliged to take refuge in that part of his kingdom. After Maḥmūd Tughlaq's return to his capital, however, a great change came about in the province of Mālwa. Dilāwar Khān declared his independence at Dhār and assumed royal titles and state in the year 804 (1401 A.D.).

With the year 804 begins the third period of the history of Mālwa, a period lasting from 804 to 937 (1401-1530) and full of important events both as regards internal affairs and relations with the neighbouring powers.

Dilāwar Khān who declared his independence and established his capital at Dhār reigned only for four years 804-8 (1401-5 A.D.). He was succeeded by his more celebrated son Alp Khān under the title of Hoshang Shāh, who transferred his capital from Dhār to Mānḍū, and ruled for thirty years 808-38 (1405-34). The sudden death of Dilāwar Khān had aroused a suspicion of his having been poisoned by Hoshang. Muḥaffar Shāh,¹ the king of Gujarāt, in consideration of the intimacy that had existed between him and the late king attacked Mālwa. Hoshang Shāh was defeated at Dhār, made prisoner and taken off to Gujarāt. Nuṣrat Shāh, Muḥaffar's brother, was appointed governor in his place. But he soon made himself unpopular and was forced to take refuge in Mānḍū. In consequence Hoshang Shāh was reinstated in 811 (1405 A.D.). During the whole of his remaining life Hoshang waged wars against the neighbouring princes and especially the king of Gujarāt. Hoshang died in 838 (1434 A.D.) and was followed by his son Ghāzī Khān under the name of Muḥammad Ghori. He was a weak ruler and was soon poisoned by his brother-in-law and prime minister Maḥmūd Khiljī² who then usurped the kingdom of Mālwa.

This new dynasty also was not destined to hold the prize long. Maḥmūd ruled very successfully for thirty-four years, 839-73 (1436-69 A.D.). He was the most illustrious of all the kings of Mālwa. He adorned his capital with many noble edifices and added many territories to his kingdom. After Maḥmūd's death his son Ghīyāthuddin ascended the throne. The whole reign of this king is marked by perfect peace in Mālwa. Neither rebellion of his subjects, nor invasions into his territories by his enemies disturbed the peace of his rule, with the one exception of Bahlol Lodi's advance from Delhi in 889 (1485 A.D.) to subdue Mālwa, an attack which was repulsed by Ghīyāthuddin.³ Many stories have been framed to describe the whimsical character of this king, but whether they are true or not our historical authorities show, that he was a strong ruler and knew well how to direct the affairs of his state.⁴ At the age of

¹ Muḥaffar Shāh of Gujarāt and Dilāwar Khān had bound themselves under an oath to be brothers in arms when they were fellow nobles in the court of Delhi. *Firishta*, Persian text, part II, p. 284.

² Maḥmūd Khiljī was the son of Malik Muḥith Khiljī. Both the father and the son were ministers of Hoshang Shāh and his successor. Hoshang Shāh was afraid of the ambitious disposition of Maḥmūd and had revealed his apprehension on his death bed. Muḥammad Ghori had also married the sister of Maḥmūd Khiljī and having given himself to excess and luxury had handed over the reins of government entirely to his prime minister and brother-in-law. The ungrateful minister's ambition got the better of his loyalty and his sense of duty and shortly after he poisoned his royal patron. *Briggs' Firishta*, Vol. IV, pp. 186, 191, 193. *Firishta*, Persian text, part II, pp. 239, 241 and 242. The story of Maḥmūd Khiljī as narrated here is also to be found in *Wāqī'āt-i-Mushṭāqī* (*Elliot's History of India*, Vol. IV, p. 562). There are however certain differences, but the account given in *Wāqī'āt* is not very reliable.

³ *Briggs' Firishta*, Vol. IV, pp. 237-8. *Firishta*, Persian text, part II, p. 257.

⁴ *Firishta*, Persian text, part II, pp. 255-7; *Tāzūk-i-Jahāngīrī*, Persian text, pp. 181-3. The statement that Ghīyāthud-din was the first of the Mālwa kings who minted gold is wrong. For the gold coins of Maḥmūd Khiljī, his father, see *Catalogue of the Coins of the Indian Museum* by Chas. J. Rodgers: Part I the Sultans of Delhi and other contemporaries, p. 126.

eighty and after a rule of more than thirty-two years, 873-903 (1469-1500 A.D.) his life was brought to an end by poison, said to have been administered by his ungrateful son and successor Nāṣiruddīn,¹ who had been entrusted with all the state affairs as a prime minister and proclaimed heir-apparent by his father. Nāṣiruddīn had to struggle for the throne with his younger brother 'Alāuddīn and having triumphed was crowned at Māndū in 906 (1500 A.D.) whilst Ghīyāthuddīn was still alive. Unlike his father, Nāṣiruddīn's whole career as a king is full of scandalous deeds, and he is said to have been drowned in a tank when in a fit of drunkenness. His reign lasted for eleven years, 906-17 (1500-11 A.D.). After the death of Nāṣiruddīn his second son Maḥmūd called A'zam Humāyūn was made king; the eldest son having revolted against his father, without succeeding, had taken refuge in Delhi. During the reign of A'zam Humāyūn, Mālwa became a scene of constant trouble. He had to fight against his own Rājput commander-in-chief and minister Medini Rai, who had become too powerful, and setting aside his (A'zam Humāyūn's) authority had almost dethroned him. With the help of the king of Gujarāt he succeeded in suppressing the Rājputs and regaining his throne. He once more fought Medini Rāi who had made himself master of Ohanderī and Gagrūn and was totally defeated and taken prisoner, but was released a little afterwards.² In 932 (1525 A.D.) A'zam Humāyūn gave protection to Ohānd Khān, the outlawed brother of the king of Gujarāt and to Raziul Mulk, a refugee noble of that court. This ungrateful conduct of A'zam Humāyūn was a prelude to the war between the two states, with the result that Māndū was taken and A'zam Humāyūn made a prisoner with his family and put to death on his way to prison at Ohampānir in 938³ (1531 A.D.). The period of Maḥmūd's real and nominal reign covered twenty years, 917-37 (1511-1531).

With the death of A'zam Humāyūn, the Khiljī line became extinct, and Mālwa was annexed to Gujarāt, till Humāyūn Shāh defeated Bahādur Shāh, the king of Gujarāt, and made a temporary conquest of Māndū in 941 (1534 A.D.). After the departure of Humāyūn one Mallū Khān, a former governor of Māndū, proclaimed himself king under the title of Qādir Shāh in 943 (1536 A.D.). In 949 (1542) Sher Shāh Sūr defeated Qādir Shāh and installed his own governor Shujā'at Khān, who was a little after expelled by Salīm Shāh, the son and successor of Sher Shāh. Salīm Shāh pardoned Shujā'at Khān, but divided the territory of Mālwa among several of his nobles. On the accession of 'Adil Shāh, Shujā'at Khān recovered Mālwa and assumed independence in 962 (1554 A.D.).⁴ He died immediately afterwards and was succeeded by his son Malik Bā-yazid known as Bāz Bahādur. In the year 968 (1560 A.D.) Khān Adham, Akbar's general defeated Bāz Bahādur and drove him out of Māndū. But in the following year Bāz Bahādur was reinstated. Hearing this, Akbar sent one of his generals 'Abdullāh Khān Uzbek against Bāz Bahādur.

¹ *Briggs' Firishta*, Vol. IV, pp. 238-9. *Firishta*, Persian text, part II, p. 268. Jahāngīr writes in his diary (*Tuzuk-i-Jahāngīrī*, Persian text, p. 181):—"It is related that when Sher Khān Afghān Sūr visited Nāṣiruddīn's tomb, he ordered his attendants to flagellate the parricide's grave. When I visited it I kicked it and ordered those with me to do the same. Not satisfied with this I ordered his bones to be dug out and burned and the ashes to be thrown into the Nerbada river." See also *Iqbāl Nāma Jahāngīrī*, Persian text (Bibl. Ind.), p. 99. *Firishta* Persian text, part II, p. 261 doubts Nāṣiruddīn's guilt on the ground that he was not present at Māndū when Ghīyāthuddīn died. He further argues that Nāṣiruddīn ruled for years after the death of his father, and as a parricide does not live in peace after his father's death, he could not have killed his father.

² *Firishta*, Persian text, part II, p. 268; English translation by Briggs, Vol. IV, pp. 262-3.

³ This event is given under the year 932 (1526 A.D.) in *Briggs' Firishta*, Vol. IV, p. 269, and the *Bombay Gazetteer*, Vol. I, Part I, p. 867. But the date 938 is given by *Mirāt-i-Sekandarī* (*Local Mohamedan Dynasties*, Gujarāt, pp. 352-3) followed by the *Imperial Gazetteer*, Vol. II, pp. 380 and 381, whilst *Firishta* (Persian text part II, p. 269) has 14th Sha'bān 937.

⁴ *Firishta*, Persian text, part II, p. 273. In the *Imperial Gazetteer*, Vol. II, pp. 380 and 381 Shujā'at Khān's expulsion is ignored and he is said to have ruled as a governor from 949 to 962 (1542-51 A.D.).

THE INSCRIPTIONS OF DHĀR AND MĀNDŪ.

Abdullāh reconquered Mālwa in 969,¹ but showed signs of assuming independence, whereupon the emperor Akbar himself marched to Māndŭ,² and incorporated Mālwa with the Mughal dominion in 971 (1562 A.D.). Bāz Bahādur after a useless struggle paid homage to the emperor Akbar at Delhi and received the command of 2,000 horse in 978 (1570 A.D.).³

This annexation brought peace to Mālwa for more than a century, 970-1102 (1562-1690 A.D.)

From the incorporation of Mālwa with the Mughal dominion to the beginning of British supremacy in India.

though now and then refractory chiefs took refuge there, owing to which Akbar was obliged to dismantle the fort of Māndŭ. It was not until the year 1102 (1690 A.D.) that disturbances broke out in Mālwa caused by the Marāṭhas, who took its capital Māndŭ in 1108 (1696 A.D.) and also reduced the fort of Dhār. Jai Singh who was despatched by the emperor Aurangzeb, repulsed the Marāṭhās, but they returned about the year 1137 (1724 A.D.) when Udaji Puar⁴ planted his standard at Māndŭ. This occupation also was shortlived, but after the succession of Bāji Rāo, the second Peshwa and the decline of the Mohamedan supremacy in Mālwa the Marāṭhās occupied it permanently. Still Mālwa did not enjoy peace as had been expected, for now it became an object of struggle among the Marāṭhā chiefs themselves. The advent of the British, however, put all the contests to an end, and we still find a descendant of the ancient Puar family on the Gaddi of Dhār.

As has already been stated first Dhār and then Māndŭ were the capitals of Mālwa. The

Dhār and Māndŭ capitals of Mālwa.

fallen entirely into ruin. The ancient buildings of both these places have been greatly damaged by the ravages of time. But now measures are being taken to preserve them as far as possible.

The climate and fertility⁵ for which Mālwa has been famous from time immemorial, and the long repute of the site and the princely buildings of its capitals (Dhār and Māndŭ) actuated the great Mughal emperors to visit the province, and some of these visits were commemorated by inscriptions⁶ included in this collection. The style of architecture in Mālwa is similar to the Pathān style employed in the earlier buildings at Delhi, and according to Fergusson,⁷ it is wanting in local individuality.

These few pages are intended only as a short historical introduction to the publication of the Arabic and Persian inscriptions found in Dhār and Māndŭ. The inscriptions have been arranged according to the age of the buildings containing them. In some cases I have found it necessary to say something of the buildings in order to make the contents of the inscriptions clearer.

The books quoted in the text or notes are mostly well known. There is only one, of which it might be necessary to give here the full title as I have not found it quoted in other books dealing with the history of Mālwa: *Tūzūk-i-Afghānī Armaghān-i-Shāhjahānī Maṭbū' dar Maṭba'-i-Mufīd-i-'Ām Press, Agra, 1293 H.*

¹ In the *Imperial Gazetteer*, Vol. II, pp. 390 and 381 the date of Bāz Bahādur's surrender is given as 1564 A.D. (972 A.H.) *Firishā*, Persian text, part I, p. 252, and *Tabaqāt-i-Akbarī* (*Elliott's History of India*, Vol. V, p. 276) record his final overthrow in 969 (1561 A.D.); and this seems to be the correct date; in another passage, however, *Firishā* (part II, p. 275) gives 970 instead of 969.

² *Āin-i-Akbarī*, English translation by Blochmann, Vol. I, p. 321.

³ *Briggs' Firishā*, Vol. IV, p. 279. *Firishā*, Persian text, part II, p. 275.

⁴ Udaji Puar, an officer in the bodyguard of the Rāja of Satārā (Sābu), became the founder of the present family of the chiefs of Dhār. E. Barnes's *Dhār and Mandu*, p. 4 n.

⁵ *Āin-i-Akbarī*, English translation by Jarrett, Vol. II, p. 199, *Tūzūk-i-Jahāngīrī*, Persian text, p. 180 seq., *Iqbāl Nāma Jahāngīrī*, Persian text (Bibl. Ind.), p. 94 seq.

⁶ See inscriptions IV, VIII, XXIV, XXV, XXVI.

⁷ *History of Indian and Eastern Architecture*, p. 431.

Most of the inscriptions given here are transcribed from rubbings taken by Dr. Führer, but as this collection was incomplete I was obliged to borrow those in the possession of Dhār state, and I am much obliged to the Darbār for kindly lending them. Another set of rubbings was taken by myself in January 1910. Dr. Führer's collection is in the office of the Director General of Archæology, Simla, as well as the rubbings taken by myself.

There are altogether 30 inscriptions published here; some few have been left out, as they did not offer any historical interest, being barely Qurānic quotations without any date or name. Of the other inscriptions the only one left out by me is that on the tomb of Abdullāh Shāh Changāl, which has been edited and translated by Maulvī Ghulām Yazdāni, M.A. (*vide* pp. 1-5). Words which I could not decipher have been marked by dots (.....), letters effaced in the inscriptions, but which I think I was able to insert by conjecture, have been included in square brackets.

I cannot conclude this introduction without expressing my deep sense of gratitude, and offering my sincere thanks to Dr. J. Horowitz for the valuable directions and kind help he has now and then given me in writing this article. I am sure that I would not have achieved half of what I have done without his kind supporting hand.

DHĀR.

The old name of this city is Dhārā Nagri (the town of the blades of swords), but it is now known among the Mohamedans as "Pirān-i-Dhār" owing to the number of the tombs of Mohamedan saints found in its vicinity. It was the capital of Mālwa both during the time of the Hindū Rājas and the Mohamedan governors of the province. Dilāwar Khān also made it the seat of his government, when he assumed independence.¹ But its prominence under the Mohamedan independent rulers was only ephemeral, as Hoşang Shāh, the successor of Dilāwar Khān, preferred Māndū, and made it his capital. The latter then continued to enjoy this distinction till the Mohamedan supremacy faded in Mālwa. Consequently Dhār is not so rich in Mohamedan architectural remains. In ancient times Dhār was famous for its fertility in producing grapes. Abul Fazl in his *Āin-i-Akbarī* says, "Dhār is a town which was the capital of Rāja Bhoja and many ancient princes. The vine here bears twice in the year when the sun first enters Pisces (February) and Leo (July), but the former of these two vintages is sweeter."²

THE FORT.

The most interesting and the most ancient building in Dhār is the fort, which is said to have been built by Muḥammad Tughlaq when he was on his way to the conquest of the Deccan. Jahāngir writes in his diary, "Its outline is very elegant, but the space inside is empty of buildings."³ The exact date of its foundation is nowhere found. The only inscription (see plate II, No. 1) it contains dates from the time of Aurangzeb; it is engraved on a piece of iron plate measuring 8" by 6" in Nasta'liq characters and runs as follows:—

I.

الله محمد

(۱) بقعه داری عاشور بیگ پر تدبیر که کوس همت او مشتری بچرخ نواخت
 (۲) بنظم مستقیم از بهر سال تاریخش حصار دهارز دروازه سر بلندی یافت
 مطابق سنه ۲۷ جلوس عالم گیر شاهی تواریخ هجری در مصرع آخراست و یافت براے
 بیت است عاشور بیگ کوکه زاده شاهجهان بادشاه

¹ *Briggs' Firishta*, Vol. IV, p. 168. *Firishta*, Persian text, part II, p. 234.

² *Āin-i-Akbarī*, English translation by Jarret, Vol. II, p. 197.

³ *Tuzuk-i-Jahāngirī*, Persian text, pp. 201-2. For full particulars about the fort see E. Barnes, *Dhār and Mandu*, pp. 7, 8.

Allah Muḥammad.

(1) "During the governorship of 'Āshūr Beg who is full of skill and prudence, and whose high-mindedness Jupiter pealed in heaven;

(2) *the fort of Dhār was graced with a gateway, the date of which is expressed by a correct verse.*

Corresponding to the 27th year of the accession of 'Ālamgir. The Hijra year is calculated from (the numerical value of the letters of) the last hemistich, and *یافت* stands for the sake of metre (only). 'Āshūr Beg, the son of the foster brother of the king Shābjahān."

The numerical value of the letters of the last hemistich is 1,586, and by deducting 491 the numerical value of the letters of the word *یافت* which is not to be reckoned, the date 1095 (1683—4 A.D.) is obtained which corresponds to the date given in numbers, *viz.*, the 27th year of 'Ālamgir's accession.

THE LĀṬ MASJID.

This mosque was built by Dilāwar Khān, the first Mohamedan king of Mālwa. Jahāngir in his diary¹ calls it Jāmi' Masjid. Its present name (Lāṭ Masjid) it owes to an iron pillar which lies near the mosque. It possesses two inscriptions, one on the eastern and the other on the northern entrance to the mosque. The former (see Plate III) which measures 53½" × 22" runs as follows :—

II.

مدار اهل زمان آفتاب برج کمال	خدایگان زمین مطلع سپهر جلال	(۱)
فلک جناب و ملک قدر و مسیم مثال	خلاصه سیرت و عالی نسب ستوده تبار	(۲)
ندیده دیده گردون چنر بلورج خیال	بعدل و بذل و وقار و رزم و بزم و شکوه	(۳)
بله چو فخر کند غور ازان حمیده خصال	پناه پشت شریعت عمید شاه دارد	(۴)
که برگزیده خدارند ایزد متعال	معین و ناصر دین نبی دلارر خان	(۵)
که بود ملجا ارتاد و مرجع ابدال	مرید شیخ طریقت نصیر دین محمود	(۶)
بروقت سعد و خجسته بروز افرخ فال	بشهر دهار بنا کرد مسجد جامع	(۷)
فزون ز وصف درعالم برون ز حد مقال	چه مسجدی که جهانراست کعبه ثانی	(۸)
که یافت عرصه گیتی از بهار جمال	مگر که مسجد اقصی و بیست معمور است	(۹)
که شد تمام ز اقبال قبله امال	گذشته بود ز تاریخ و سال هیصد و هفت	(۱۰)
خداش ثبت کند در جریده اعمال	بعق احمد مرسل که طاعت و حسنات	(۱۱)

¹ *Tuzuk-i-Jahāngiri*, Persian text, pp. 201-2. For further details see Fergusson, *History of Indian and Eastern Architecture*, p. 541 and E. Barnes, *Dhār and Mandu*, pp. 9-10, where an English translation of the inscription is also given.

- (1) "The Lord of the earth and the place of rising of the sphere of glory; the support of the people of the age and the sun of the zodiac of perfection;
- (2) the essence of (good) qualities, belonging to a noble family and a celebrated lineage having dignity (as high) as sky, rank (as exalted as that) of angels and resembling the Messiah;
- (3) whose equal in justice, charity, dignity and magnificence, in war and peaceful entertainments, the eye of heaven hath never seen even on the board of imagination;
- (4) the asylum for the law of the (Mohamedan) religion 'Amīdahāh Dāūd,—Ghor may well be proud of a man of such laudable qualities—
- (5) the supporter and helper of the religion of the prophet Dilāwar Khān who is the chosen one of the most high God;
- (6) and the disciple of that head of a holy order Naṣir Din Maḥmūd, who was a refuge of the grandees and retreat of the saints¹;
- (7) built a Jāmi' Masjid in the city of Dbār at a fortunate and auspicious moment and on the day of a happy omen.
- (8) What a beautiful mosque! the second ka'ba of the world! higher than the praises of both the worlds and beyond the limits of expression.
- (9) Perhaps it is Masjid-i-Aqṣā² and the heavenly prototype of the temple of Mecca that earth got worth and beauty on account of it.
- (10) With regard to date 807 years had passed (from the Hijra) (1404—5 A.D.) when this mosque was completed through the good fortune of the centre of hopes (the king.)
- (11) May God through the intercession of Muḥammad the prophet, enter worship and good works in his (the king's) book of deeds.³"

The inscription on the northern entrance to the Lāṭ-Masjid is also of the time of Dilāwar Khān. It has been very badly damaged, and the characters in some places are quite obliterated (see Plate IV). I was able to make out the portion transcribed below from the stone. The inscription measures 14" × 18".

III.

بنده امیدوار رحمت پروردگار عمید شاه دارد غروری خالصاً تعالی در شهر دهار
 . . . حرسه الله عن الافات والبلیات این مسجد جامع بنا کرد هر که استمداد بدعا [ر] [ن] بهر درام
 . . . این مسجد . . . جل و علا او را ماجور و مغفور گرداند بمنذوگتره فی الخامس
 عشر من شهر . . . رجب رجب قدره سنه سبع و ثمانمائه

¹ *Abdāl*—"Certain persons by whom God continues the world in existence. (Their number is 70; of which 40 reside in Syria and 30 elsewhere. When any one of them dies, his place is filled up by some one selected from among the rest of mankind)" *Persian-English Dictionary*, by F. Steingass. "According to Abul Bakā, as stated by El-Munāwee, it seems that they meant (by this appellation) the substitutes and successors of the prophets; and according to some, they were seven, neither more nor fewer, by means of whom God takes care of the seven climates; one being successor of Abraham (El-khaleel) and to him pertains the first climate, the second of Moses (El-Keleem); the third of Aaron; the fourth of Idrees; the fifth of Joseph; the sixth of Jesus, and the seventh of Adam." *Arabic-English Lexicon*, by E. W. Lane. See also *Encyclopædia of Islām* s. v. *Abdāl*.

² *Masjid-i-Aqṣā*, the most remote temple in Jerusalem.

³ A book of the actions of mankind, supposed to be kept by the guardian or observing angels, to be produced on the Day of Judgment. Some verses of this inscription have been included by Jahāugir in his diary (*Tuzuk-i-Jahāngīrī*, p. 189), but the following words have been wrongly transcribed there; line first کورب for سپهر and برج for برج, line fourth که افتخار for چه فخر, line seventh بروز for بوقت and بوقت for بروز, line tenth هشتمد for هیصم and درکه for قبله. The text of this inscription is also found in *Armaghān-i-Shāhjahānī*, p. 101, where the learned author has made some mistakes in reading.

“Amid Shāh Dāūd Ghori, the slave who is confident of the mercy of the (Almighty) Protector made this Jāmi‘ Masjid purely for the most high God in the city of Dhār . . . may God save it from evils and calamities. Every one who prays for the perpetuity . . . this mosque . . . may the most high and glorious God remunerate him, and forgive him his sins. In Mandū Garh on the 15th of the month . . . Rajab of honoured rank of the year 807 (17th Jan. 1405 A.D.)”

At a distance of about 80 ft. from the northern gate of the Lāṭ Masjid there lies a square beam of iron from which the mosque derived its present name. It is not certain for which purpose this pillar was originally meant. Fergusson says,¹ “This is generally supposed to have been a pillar of victory, like that at Kuṭb, but this can hardly be the case.” He further remarks, “My impression is that it was used for some useful constructive purpose.” Jahāngir in his diary (*Tuzuk-i-Jahāngiri* Persian text, pp. 201-2) speaks of it as follows:—

“Outside this fort (the fort of Dhār) there is a Jāmi‘ Masjid which has in front of it fixed in the ground a four-cornered column about four feet round. When Sulṭān Bahādur of Gujarāt took Mālwa he wished to carry the column to Gujarāt. In the course of its being dug up the pillar fell and broke into two, one piece measuring 22 ft., the other 13 ft. As it was lying here uncared for, I (Jahāngir) ordered the big piece to be carried to Agra to be put in the courtyard of the shrine of him (Akbar) whose abode is the heavenly throne, to be utilized as a lamp post.”

The orders of Jahāngir were not carried out. The big piece is lying where Jahāngir saw it, and the second piece has been removed to the Agency garden.² The piece lying *in situ* has an inscription measuring 11" × 9". No rubbing of it could be taken as the characters engraved are too faint.

IV.

در زمانیکہ اعلیٰ حضرت خاقانی ظل سبحانی شان مظهر حق شاہ اکبر تعالیٰ شانہ اللہ اکبر
عازم دکن برد بتاریخ ہشتم اسفندار مذ سنہ ۳۴ جلوسی مرافق سنہ ۱۰۰۸ ہجری درین
مقام نزل اجلال فرمودند عمل دارد کندہ کار [حرره] محمد [معصوم] نامی بکری

“During the time when His Exalted Majesty, the Khāqān, the shadow of God, the glory of the manifestation of the Almighty, the king Akbar, whose rank is exalted, Allāhu Akbar was on his way to the Deccan, he alighted here with great pomp on the 8th Isfandār Muz,³ in the 44th year of his accession, corresponding to 1008 Hijra (15th Feb. 1600 A.D.) This is the work of Dāūd, the sculptor, (the text has been) composed by Muḥammad Ma‘ṣūm Nāmī Bakrī.”

¹ Fergusson, *History of Indian and Eastern Architecture*, p. 541.

² E. Barnes, *Dhār and Mandu*, p. 10.

³ *Isfandār Muz* is the name of the 12th Persian month of the solar year, when the sun enters Pisces (February). In *Armaghān-i-Shāhjahāni* and E. Barnes, *Dhār and Mandu*, the name of this month is wrongly transcribed “اسفندیار (Isfandyār)” and “42 Julūsī corresponding to 1000 Hijra” is given there as the date, but “44th Julūsī corresponding to 1008 Hijra” is corroborated by other inscriptions, *vis.* VIII. XXIV.

⁴ Mohammad Ma‘ṣūm was a very famous poet and composer of inscriptions in the time of Akbar. *Āin-i-Akbarī*, English translation by Blochmann, Vol. I. p. 514. His poetic name was Nāmī and Bakrī was the family title, *i.e.* the descendant of Abū Bakr the 1st Caliph. His full name and titles are given in the inscription found on the left pillar of the central inner arch of the Buland Darwāzah in Fathpur Sikri. His name is also mentioned in the inscription No. VIII.

KĀMĀL MAULA.¹

The tomb of Kamāluddīn Mālvi lies within a shrine surrounded by a wall on all sides. There are many tombs within this enclosure and its vicinity, but none of them contains any inscription worth recording. Quotations from the Qurān, no doubt, are to be found in more than one place, but they offer no historical interest whatever. The main entrance to the enclosure bears the following inscription measuring 67" x 30" (see Plate V).

V.

الله ولي المومنين

- (۱) این روضه رضوان چنین زیب و جمال
 رین قبه پر نور چنین قطب کمال
 (۲) چون از پے زایران مسکین و غریب
 در ساحت و صحن تنگ بودست مجال
 (۳) این هر در رزاق و صحن وین گنبد نور
 با پرده سنگ و خانه و آب زلال
 (۴) زان **صحنه** درون و خانقاه و دهلیز
 باکشک و باکنگره هر یک چو هلال
 (۵) هم از پے اسایش هر اهل دله
 هم از پے مشغولیه هر صاحب حال
 (۶) در عهد همایون خود آن شاهجهان
 محمود شه خلجی و خورشید مثال
 (۷) در هیصد رستین ریک آراست ز سر
 آراسته باد قصر عمرش همه سال
 (۸) بر درکه این در شاه دین و دنیا
 محمود گدا فتاده در صف نعال
 (۹) چون هست صلاح عام زین در همه را
 باشد که به بور رکن گویند تعال
- کتبه و عمل . . . الحافظ الشیرازی المرشدی فی سنه . . .

"God is the helper of the believers (Mohamedans).

(1) This is a Garden of Paradise, of such elegance and beauty, and this is the vault full of light of such a Quṭb² Kamāl.

(2) As room had become scanty for the poor and needy pilgrims in the courtyard and quadrangle;

(3) both the gallery and courtyard, and this bright dome with stone screen, the cells and pure water;³

¹ The full name of this saint is Shaiḫ Kamāludīn Mālvi. Maula seems to be the corrupt form of Mālwi, as he was called because of his residence in Mālwa. He was a disciple of Shaiḫ Niẓāmud-dīn Auliya of Delhi. See *Āin-i-Akbari*, English translation by Jarret, Vol. III, p. 365. Seven verses of the inscription have been published in *Armughān-i-Shāhjahānī*, pp. 103-4, with various mistakes. According to the *Mirāt-i-sikandarī* (see *Local Muhammadan dynasties, Gujarāt* by Bayley, p. 131) the tomb of Shaiḫ Kamāl of Mālwa is "at the back of the Jāmi' masjid of Khudāwand Khān . . . at 'I'impura in the environs of Ahmadābād."

² "In the conventional language of the mystics, the name Quṭb is applied to the hierarch of the saints, who is also called Aighnauth (الغوث) and is supposed to be pre-eminently endowed with sanctity and with thaumaturgic faculties; and to be known Quṭb to none but his agents unless he make himself known: at his death his place is believed to be filled by another." *Arabic-English lexicon* by E. W. Lane.

³ By *Āb-i-zulāl* here is most probably meant the water of the narrow deep well within the enclosure. It is a common belief of the people, that he who will take a draught of it is sure to get salvation.

(4) and that interior raised floor, and the monastery and vestibule with the upper chambers and turrets each like the new moon ;

(5) both for the repose of all men of piety and for the occupation of all devout Sūfis ;

(6) during his august reign that king of the world Maḥmūd Shāh Khiljī who resembles the sun,

(7) embellished them anew in the year 861 (1456—7 A.D.). May the palace of his age ever remain embellished !

(8) On the threshold of these two kings¹ of the religion and of the world the beggar Maḥmūd lies prostrate in the row of shoes.²

(9) As there is a general proclamation from this door to all, it may be that the pillars (the aforesaid kings of the religion and the world) say to the helpless (Maḥmūd) " Rise and come."

Writing and work of . . . al-Hāfiẓ al-Shīrāzi in the year . . ."

There is also a fragmentary inscription written on a broken piece of stone, which has been placed inside the enclosure of Kamāl Maulā. As, however, the complete text of this inscription has been carved on the Tārāpur gate Māndū, the fragment is omitted here, while the whole of it will be published among the Māndū inscriptions (see Inscription IX).

Kamāl Maula contains also the oldest Mohamedan inscription of Dhār. This is said to have " been exhumed from the small grave-yard in this enclosure."³ It shows that Maḥmūd (Tughlaq) was the ruling king in the year 795 (1392—3 A.D.) when Dilāwar Khān as his governor repaired the mosques in Dhār. The historians⁴ who assert that he became king in 796 are wrong : not only our inscription but also a coin⁵ preserved in the Indian Museum proves that he was king already in 795. The last verse is much obliterated (see Plate II. No. 2), and I am sorry that I could not decipher the whole of it. The inscription measures 21" × 15½".

VI.

که ضبط ملک جهان حق بدر میسر کرد	بعهد دولت محمود شاه بن سلطان	(۱)
که جور دور سپهرین خراب و ابر کرد	بشهر دهار مساجد که بود دیرینه	(۲)
که حمله مالوه را باز تازه از سر کرد	نمود خان فلک منزلت دلار خان	(۳)
عما کرد	بسال هفتصد و پنج فرد . . خدای	(۴)

¹ It is not known who this other saint alluded to here is. Possibly it may be Maulānā Ḥusāmuddīn whose tomb is also there.

² "Opposite that of Kamāluddīn stands a tomb which, local tradition insists, is that of Maḥmūd Khiljī himself. Again, to quote tradition, the great warrior is said to have expressed the wish that he should be buried in the place where people removed their shoes in going to visit the tomb of his patron saint Kamāl-ud-dīn." E. Barnes, *Dhār and Mandu*, p. 12.

³ E. Barnes, *Dhār and Mandu*, p. 11n.

⁴ *Firihā*, Persian text, part I, p. 154 ; *Tārīkh Muḥārak Shāhī*, Elliot's *History of India*, Vol. IV, pp. 27-8 ; *Local Mohamedan Dynasties, Gujarat*, by Bayley, pp. 75-6 ; *Imperial Gazetteer*, Vol. II, p. 369.

⁵ *Catalogue of the Coins of the Indian Museum*, by Chas. J. Rodgers, Part I, the Sultāns of Delhi and other Contemporaries, p. 73.

⁶ The inscription reads clearly *حمله* but apparently *جمله* is meant.

(1) "During the reign of Maḥmūd Shāh, the son of a Sulṭān, to whom God entrusted the control of the world.

(2) In the city of Dhār the mosques which were old, and were ruined and made desolate by the tyranny of the revolution of sky,

(3) the Khān of rank high as sky, Dilāwar Khān, who again renewed the whole of Mālwa, rebuilt them.

(4) In the year 795 (1392—3 A.D.) . . . God made."

Close to the Barwāli Masjid there are some tombs and there is one inscription mentioning the names of four men who are buried there and giving the date of their death. The upper part of this inscription is in verse and measures $15'' \times 5''$, the lower one in prose measures $11\frac{1}{2}'' \times 5\frac{1}{2}''$ (see Plate II. No. 3).

VII.

سنه ۱۰۰۰ بتاریخ ۲۷ ذی الحجه	(۱) خضر خان و مجاهد خان و برهان	جلال الدین که هر یک یار غار اند
	(۲) زه یاری که بعد از جان سپردن	بیگجا خفته اندر خاک دهار اند
	(۳) زمن از جرئت اینان چه یرسی	که هر یک رستم و اسفندیار اند
	(۴) بجان بازی ایشان آفرین باد	چه نیکو آمده در رزم کار اند
	(۵) خرد تاریخ سال فوتشان گفت	شنیدی پاک و اکبر هر چهار اند

لا اله الا الله محمد رسول الله

مرحومي مغفوري شيخ برهان بشهادت رسيد

لا اله الا الله محمد رسول الله

تاریخ شهادت مرحومي خضر خان ولد منصور خان برادر زاده ابراهيم خان برزالي

روز سه شنبه بست هفتم شهر ذی الحجه سنه ۱۰۰۰ هجري

(1) "Khizr Khān, Mujāhid Khān, Burhān and Jalāluddīn who are intimate friends.

(2) O what friendship! Even after death they are sleeping (buried) together in the dust of Dhār.

(3) What doest thou enquire of me about their valour? each of them is a Rustam and Isfandyār.¹

(4) Praise be to their intrepidity! How good they have proved in the strife.

(5) Wisdom announced the date of their death saying, "Did you hear, all the four are pure and great." (1095.)

There is no God but God and Muḥammad is his prophet.

On the 27th Zūl Hijjah of the year 1000² Shaikh Burhān, the defunct of happy memory whose sins have been forgiven, died martyr.

There is no God but God and Muḥammad is his prophet.

¹ Isfandyār, the son of Ghustasp, was a king of Persia, and was killed by Rustam.

² Possibly 1100 is meant. This date is written alongside the inscription; perhaps there was no room for it on Burhān's stone.

THE INSCRIPTIONS OF DHĀR AND MĀNDŪ.

Date of the martyrdom of Khizr Khān, the defunct of happy memory, the son of Maṅṅūr Khān, the nephew of Ibrāhīm Khān, Barwāli, Tuesday, the 27th Zūl Hijjah year 104.¹

SĀDAL PUR.

This village is situated 12 miles north-east of Dhār on the Mhow-Nimach road. Of ancient remains it contains a water palace on which there is an inscription written on two slabs (see Plate VI) measuring 37" by 27½" and 31" by 11" respectively.

VIII.

بندگان حضرت شاهنشاه خلافت پناه ظل الله جلال الدين محمد اكبر بادشاه در حين توجه
تسخير دکن اين منزل را بعز قدوم رشک فردوس برين ساختند و کان ذلك في تاريخ اوایل
(سفندار مذ سنه ۴۴ الهی موافق سنه ۱۰۰۸ حرره محمد معصوم نامي بکري
(۱) نامي بکشا چشم بصيرت در ياب بنياد زمانه همچو نقشی است بر آب
(۲) باتر گويم که حاصل دنيا چيست بيداری يکزمان ر باقی همه خواب

"The slaves of His Most Exalted Majesty, the protection of the Califate, the Shadow of God, Jalāluddin Muḥammad Akbar, the king, while on their way to the conquest of the Deccan made this place by the honour of their visit the envy of paradise. This happened in the beginning of Isfandār Muz of the year 44 Ilāhī² corresponding to 1008 (8th Feb. 1600 A.D.). Written by Muḥammad Ma'sūm Nāmī Bakri.

(1) Nāmī! Open your eyes of prudence and behold that the foundation of the world is like a figure drawn on water.

(2) I tell you what the sum and substance of the world is, "Wakefulness for a short time and then all sleep."

MĀNDŪ.

This old noble city has undergone so many phases of prosperity and adversity that it is hardly possible to describe them in detail in this short note, and we must confine ourselves to a few remarks.

The time when the city rose to significance began shortly after the province of Mālwa threw off its allegiance to the throne of Delhi. It was on the accession of Alp Khān known as Hoshang Shāh in the year 808 (1405 A.D.), that Māndū was made the capital of Mālwa. Seven years previous to this date Alp Khān had repaired to this place annoyed with his father Dilāwar Khān at his entertaining Maḥmūd Tughlaq, the refugee king of Delhi as his overlord at Dhār. According to Firishā³ Hoshang stayed there during the residence of Maḥmūd Tughlaq

¹ Possibly again 1104 is meant. The two dates given in the prose part differ by 5 and 9 respectively from the date contained in the chronogram. The meaning may be that only Mujāhid Khān and Jalāluddin died in 1095, whilst the two others who died later had the dates of their death recorded separately. The inscription of Khizr Khān has been carved twice, apparently for the sake of symmetry.

² Akbar introduced a new era which was called *Ilāhī* era. It begins from the 5th Rabi' the second 963 A.H. (19th February 1556), i.e. the date of Akbar's accession. According to the table published as an appendix to J. A. S. it was established in the 80th of Akbar's reign, i.e. 993 A.H. *Āin-i-Akbarī* by Jarret, Vol. II. p. 1n.

³ *Briggs' Ferishā*, Vol. IV. p. 169. *Firishā*, Persian text, part II, p. 234.

in Mālwa, and it was at this time that he laid the foundation of that celebrated fortress which was completed when he became king. Although Dilāwar Khān on assuming his independence had taken up his residence at Dhār, and made that place the seat of his government, he frequently visited Māṇḍū remaining there sometimes for months together,¹ and inscriptions preserved to us prove that he also erected some buildings there.²

Once chosen, Māṇḍū remained the capital of Mālwa till the latter was incorporated with the Mughal dominions and lost its independence.

The rulers of Mālwa, like the kings of other Mohamedan dynasties in India, unscrupulously lavished their treasures in embellishing their capital with ornate and noble edifices. Sultān Ghiyāthuddīn added much to the grandeur and splendour of this city, and it was during the time of this king that Māṇḍū justified its name of Shādiābād (the abode of pleasure).

Though in the time of Akbar Māṇḍū was still a sarkār,³ and also had a mint,⁴ where copper coins were struck, yet it is evident that it lost all its lustre with the final overthrow of Bāz Bahādūr in 970 (1562 A.D.). Jahāngīr visited it in the year 1025 (1616 A.D.). He writes in his diary⁵ that three lakhs of rupees were spent in repairing some of the old buildings and on new constructions. To a large extent these buildings owe it to these repairs that they have lasted up to the present time. Māṇḍū has been quite deserted since the Mohamedan supremacy came to an end there. Colonel Briggs gives the following description of it in the year 1827 :—

“Perhaps no part of India so abounds with tigers at present as the vicinity of the once famous city of Mandu. This capital, now deserted by men, is overgrown by forest trees; and from being the seat of luxury, elegance, and wealth, has become the abode of wild beasts, and is resorted to by the few Europeans in that quarter of the world for the purpose of enjoying the pleasure of destroying them. Instances have been known of the tigers being so bold as to carry off troopers riding in the ranks of their regiments.”⁶

Since then things have again changed as the following remarks of Captain Barnes⁷ show :—

“The times have changed. No tiger has been seen in Mandu for the last thirty years, and the once famous capital is now the head-quarters of a small Tehsil of the Dhar state.”

Māṇḍū is situated on a hill round which runs a battlemented wall nearly 28 miles in circuit. The access to it is through three strong gateways, *s.g.*, Tārāpur gate, Delhi gate, and Bhagwanpā gate. Each of these contains one or two inscriptions which are here transcribed.

¹ Briggs' *Ferishāta*, Vol. IV. p. 168. *Ferishāta*, Persian text, part II, p. 234.

² See inscriptions IX and XIII.

³ *Āin-i-Akbarī*, English Translation by Jarret, Vol. II. p. 206.

⁴ *Op. cit.* Vol. I. pp. 81-2. There are coins of Humāyūn and Jahāngīr struck in the mint of Māṇḍū; (see *The Coins of the Mogul Emperors of India* collected by Chas. J. Rodgers, pp. 12, 14 and 127), but there seems to be none of Akbar.

⁵ *Tuzuk-i-Jahāngīrī*, Persian text, p. 180; see also *Iqbāl-nāma Jahāngīrī*, Persian text (Bibl. Ind), p. 96.

⁶ Briggs' *Ferishāta*, Vol. IV. p. 235n.

⁷ E. Barnes, *Dhar and Mandu*, p. 40.

TĀRĀPUR GATE.¹

On a stone slab fixed on an arch. The inscription² measures 28' by 23" (see Plate VII. No. 2).

IX.

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|-----|
| مدار ملت اسلام و زبده اعیان | (۱) |
| سپهر مجد و معالی و معدن احسان | |
| جهان کشا رجوان بخت آسمان رتبت | (۲) |
| قضا توان و قدر قدرت و قوام جهان | |
| پناه شرع پیغامبر معین دین هدیه | (۳) |
| سحاب جود و سما کرم دلارخان | |
| بشهر شادیاباد دروازه مرتب کرد | (۴) |
| در رخ دولتآباد کس نداد نشان | |
| گذشته بود ز تاریخ [س]ال هیصد و نه | (۵) |
| که شد تمام ز اقبال خاصه یزدان | |

(1) "The centre of the religion of Islām and the cream of the nobles; the sky of grandeur and eminence and the mine of beneficence;

(2) The conqueror of the world, fortunate, and high as the sky in rank; powerful as fate, mighty as destiny and prop of the world;

(3) The refuge of the law of the prophet and the helper of the true religion; the cloud of bounty and the sky of generosity Dilāwar Khān

(4) Constructed in the city of Shhādīābād a gate, an equal to which no one could find in Daulatābād.³

(5) With regard to date 809 years (1406—7 A.D.) had passed from the (Hijrat) when by the good fortune of the one whom God had selected (the king) it was finished."

There is another inscription measuring 22' by 21" (see Plate VII. No. 1) on a piece of stone built into a side wall of Tārāpur gate.

X.

- در زمانه دولت و سلطنت بندگان حضرت ظل الهی جلال الدین محمد اکبر بادشاه غازی
 خلداله ملکه این فقیر حقیر طاهر محمد حسین عماد الدین بن سلطان علی سبزراری بعنایت
 سبحانی باصلاح شاه [س]راه توفیق یافت تحریر فی التاريخ شهر محرم الحرام سنه هزار چهارده

"During the reign and sovereignty of the slaves of His Majesty the shadow of God, Jalāluddīn Muḥammad Akbar, the Emperor and champion of faith— may God preserve his kingdom—! this humble beggar Ṭāhir Muḥammad Ḥusain 'Imāduddīn, son of Sultān 'Alī Sabzwāri was, by the grace of God, successful in repairing this high road. Written in the holy month of Muḥarram of the year 1014 (Muḥarram of 1014 A. H. began on 9th May 1605 A.D.)."

¹ "On the southern face of the hill overlooking Nimar and the Nerbada valley are the Bhagwanīa and Tarapur gates, named after the two villages at the foot of the hill to which each of them leads." E. Barnes, *Dhār and Mandu*, p. 42.

² About the duplicate copy of this inscription see above p. 15. In the second hemistich of verse 4 it reads در ... افاق کس نداد نشان otherwise there are no variant readings.

³ The original name of this city was Deogiri. Muḥammad Ibn Tughluq made it his capital in 1339 A.D. and changed its name to Daulatābād. *Imperial Gazetteer*, vol. xi. p. 200.

DELHI GATE.

This gate is also called 'Ālamgīr gate as it was repaired during the reign of that emperor. The inscription (see Plate VIII. No. 2) it bears is carved on a white stone slab built into a side wall and measures 24½" by 13½".

XI.

- (۱) در زمان شاه عالمگیر خاقان جهان از سرنوگشت برپا این در گردون نشان
 (۲) در هزار هفتاد و نه آغاز رهم انجام یافت ز اهتمام خان عالیشان محمد بیگ خان
 (۳) در جلوس این شهنشاہ جهان اورنگزیب بود سال یازده از روی تحریر و بیان

(1) "During the reign of 'Ālamgīr the Khāqān (the king) of the whole world, this gate resembling the sky was built anew.

(2) In the year 1079 (1668—9 A.D.) (the work of restoration) was commenced and finished under the supervision of the exalted Khān Muḥammad Beg Khān.

(3) Since the accession of this emperor of the world Aurangzeb, it was the 11th year by way of writing and speaking."

BHAGWANYĀ GATE.

The inscription (see Plate VIII. No. 1) measures 13" by 11½".

XII.

- در عمل سیادت و نقابت پناه مرزا محمد ولد مرزا بدیع الزمان مشهدی باهتمام بنده
 باخلاص محمد حسین مشهدی تعمیر یافت راقعه بتاریخ ۱۳ جمادی الثانی

"During the governorship of Mirzā Muḥammad, the protection of rule and leadership, the son of Mirzā Badī'uzzamān Mashhādī (this gate) was built under the supervision of the sincere slave Muḥammad Husain Mashhādī. This was in . 013 Jumādā II . ."

MOSQUE OF DILĀWAR KHĀN.

The following inscription (see Plate XII. No. 1) measuring 28" by 22½" is over the eastern entrance to this mosque. Some words in lines 4 and 5 did not come out well in the rubbing but are legible on the stone.

XIII.

- (۱) مدار شرع پیغامبر پناه عرصه گیهان فلک رفعت ملک طلعت نصیرالدین دلاور خان
 (۲) ممد افعال محمردش ممد اقبال موصوفش همه اوقات معمورش بخیر و طاعت یزدان
 (۳) بگرد این مسجد جامع بنا در قلعه ماندن که پیشکبیت معمور است فرود این گنبد دران
 (۴) مرتب شد بسال هیصد و هشت این بنا عالی بوقت سعد و عیمرن و بعون قادر رحمان
 (۵) بعدش حافظ و ناصر . . . باد . . . بعق عیسی مریم بعق موسی عمران

(1) "Naṣīruddin Dilāwar Khān, the centre of the law of the prophet, the refuge of the world, high as sky in dignity and angel-like appearance,

(2) Whose praiseworthy deeds and laudable good fortune are his helpers, and whose time is devoted to good purposes and worship of God,

(3) Built this Jāmi'Masjid in the fort of Māndū, which (Jāmi'Masjid,) is certainly the ka'ba beneath this revolving dome.

(4) By the help of the Almighty, the Merciful, this noble edifice was completed at an auspicious and happy time in the year 808 (1405—6 A.D.).

(5) For the sake of Jesus, the son of Maria, and Moses, the son of Imrān . . . may be . . . preserver and helper of his justice."

MOSQUE OF HUMĀYŪN KHĀN.

To the east of Sāgar lake near the camping ground stands the mosque of Ulugh A'zam Humāyūn Khān, the father of Maḥmūd Khiljī. The eastern entrance to the mosque bears the following inscription¹ (see Plate IX.) which measures 28½" by 21".

XIV.

- (۱) بقال خوب و وقت سعد و فرخ سال و مه اکرم چهارم ماه شهرالله روز جمعه اکبر
 (۲) سنین سی و پنج و هیصد و شش ماه از هجرت شمرده بود روز ماه در حکم عرب یکسر
 (۳) که شد این مسجد اسلام را بنیاد در عالم که سقف گنبد او سود سر با گنبد اخضر
 (۴) بنا مسند عالی مغیث الدین والدنیا الخ اعظم همایون خان هفت اقلام و نه کشور
 (۵) زدست همت او شد مرتب اینچنین مسجد که کس دارالامان خواند کس کعبه کند بار
 (۶) مرتب شد بسنخ ماه شوال این بنا شاه که باد این خیر اندر نامه اعمال خان مضر
 (۷) مزین از ثنا و خطبه محمود شه بادا بود تا بر زمین کوه تابد تا بچرخ اختر

(1) "With good omens, and at an auspicious time, and in a happy year and a noble month on the great day of Friday, the fourth of the month of God (Rajab).

(2) It was in the year 835 (7th Mar. 1432 A.D.) and 6 months from Hijra; the days of the month having been counted according to the Arabic (lunar) system,

(3) that this mosque of Islām was founded in the world, the roof of whose dome rubbed its head against the green vault (of heaven).

(4) It was built by Masnad-i-'Āli Mughīthuddin-wad-dunyā Ulugh² A'zam Humāyūn, the Khān of seven climes and nine regions (the whole world).

(5) With his enterprising hand such a mosque was erected that one calls it Dārul Amān (the mansion of safety) whilst others believe it to be the k'aba.

(6) At the end of the month of Shawwāl this mosque built by the king was completed. May this good deed be inserted in the Khān's book of actions.

(7) May Maḥmūd Shāh be ever adorned with praises and Khuṭba, so long as mountains stand on the earth and stars shine in the firmament."

¹ This inscription is also given in *Armaghān-i-Shāhjahānī* (p. 108), but there are various mistakes.

² *Ulugh*, a Türkī word, meaning "great".

JAMI' MASJID.

This great mosque, as the inscription which it bears shows, was commenced by Hoshang Shāh and completed by Maḥmūd Khilji. The inscription is found on the eastern entrance to the mosque. It seems to have been carved on two slabs of stone joined together, but one of these containing the first half of the inscription fell down and disappeared. The other is *in situ* and contains 5½ verses or 11 hemistiches. It is apparent (see Plate XI) that there were originally 11 verses or 22 hemistiches. The author of *Armaghān-i-Shāhjahāni* (pp. 105-6) quotes still 9 out of these 11 verses, but probably he took the text from some older chronicle, not from the stone. I give here all the 9 verses, including in brackets those which I copy from *Armaghān* and marking by dots verses 2 and 10 which are not to be found in *Armaghān* either. This inscription has been written in order to show that Maḥmūd Khilji had been entrusted with the administration of the state by Hoshang Shāh (see verses 5, 6 and 7), when he (Hoshang) was on his death-bed. The stone *in situ* measures 39" by 42".

XV.

- (۱) (مسجد عالی بنا و معبد عالی مقام) هست هر رکن حطیمش نسخه بیت الحرام
 (۲)
 (۳) از در تعظیم و قدرش چون کبوتر در حرم قدسیان اندر طواف از همه عمره تمام
 (۴) (بانی این بیت اقلس خسرو غوری هوشنگ ثانی محمود مسعود و شهاب الدین و سام)
 (۵) ز اقتضای حادثات دور بے مهر فلک چون برآمد آفتاب عمر از بلاد بام
 (۶) (گفت با محمود خلجی نور عینین مغیث از ره روشن دلی آن شاه دارا احتشام)
 (۷) ضبط ملک اتمام عمرات و دفع دشمنان میکنم بر تو وصیت من بجهت و اهتمام
 (۸) (هم برای اتمام مسجد جامع که من طرح آن افکنده ام چون مسجد والای شام)
 (۹) صورت الطاف حق سلطان علا الدین که هست مظهر انوار دین مرات حاجات انام
 (۱۰)
 (۱۱) کرد در تاریخ سال ز هشتاد و پنجاه و هشت هم بحکم این وصیت این عمارت را تمام

(1) "The mosque of exalted construction and the place of worship of high position, every pillar of the surrounding wall of which is a copy of the (pillars of the) sacred temple of Mecca.

(2)

(3) Out of respect for it and on account of its dignity the angels like the pigeons in the k'aba are always hovering around it in a sacred procession.¹

(4) The founder of this sacred building (was) the king Hoshang Ghori, (who was) the second Maḥmūd, Mas'ūd, Shihābuddin and Sām.²

(5) When as a result of events born by the revolution of the merciless sky, the sun of his life had ascended the height of the roof (was ready to set, i.e. he was about to die).

(6) That king (Hoshang) possessed of the pomp and glory of Dārā foresightedly said to Maḥmūd Khilji, the light of the eyes (the son) of Mugith.

¹ *Tawāf* and *'Umra* are two religious ceremonies performed at Mekka. The former is the procession round the k'aba to be performed seven times, the three first in a quick and the four last in a grave pace. The latter is a religious visit to some sacred places; it is also called small Haj.

² *I.e.* Maḥmūd Ghaznavi, son of Sabuktigin (388—421 H., 998—1030 A.D.); Mas'ūd, son of Maḥmūd (421—432 H., 1030—1040 A.D.); Shihābuddin Ghori (599-602 H., 1202-1206); Sām, the father of Shihābuddin.

(7) "The administration of the country and bringing its cultivation to perfection, and the driving away of the enemies are the things, to perform which, I give you my parting advice with all earnestness ;

(8) and also to complete the Jami' Masjid the foundation of which I have laid like that of the great mosque of Damascus."

(9) The personification of the kindness of Providence Sultān 'Alāuddīn who is the manifestation of the refulgence of faith, and the mirror that reflects the wants of people (realizes the wants of people and satisfies them).

(10)

(11) In the year 858 (1454 A.D.) he finished (the construction of) this building according to that parting advice."

QHARBA MASJID.

Near the great mosque lies the Maqbara of Hoshang Shāh, locally known as Qharba Masjid. It is surrounded on all sides by a wall, within which there is a large number of tombs, none however bearing any inscription. Only the shrine of Hoshang Ghori has an inscription written on the right-hand side of the doorway in very small letters (see Plate XVII. No. 2) and measuring 7" by 4½".

XVI.

بتاریخ نهم ربیع الثانی سنه هزار و هفتاد هجری فقیر حقیر لطف الله مهندس ابن استاد
احمد معمار شاه جهانی و خواجه جادوراء و استاد شیررام و استاد حامد بجهت زیارت آمده بود و
در کلمه یادگار نوشت

"On the ninth of Rabi' II of the year 1070 Hijra (14th Dec. 1659 A.D.) the humble beggar Luṭfullāh, engineer, the son of Ustād Aḥmad, architect of Shāhjahān, Khawāja Jādū Rāi, Ustād Sheo-Rām and Ustād Ḥāmid had come on pilgrimage (to the tomb), and wrote these few words to commemorate it."

ASHRAFI MAḤALL.

Opposite the Jāmi' Masjid amongst the ruins of the Ashrafi Maḥall and the tomb of Maḥmūd Khiljī, there is a large number of white stone slabs engraved with Qurānic quotations. There is only one inscription (see Plate XVII. No. 1) measuring 24" by 17½" engraved on the right-hand side of the window in the eastern wall of the Ashrafi Maḥall.

XVII.

بر تماشایان فیروزه رراق پوشیده نماید که در زمان دولت و سلطنت حضرت خلافت
پناهی ظل الهی جلال الدین محمد اکبر پادشاه غازی فقیر حقیر محمد طاهر الدین
حسین ابن سلطان علی سبزواری توفیق تعمیر این بقایای عالی یافت در ماه محرم سال
هزار و چهارده

"Let it not remain hidden from those that look up to the azure vault (the sky), that during the reign of His Majesty, the protection of the Califate, the shadow of God Jalāluddīn

Muhammad Akbar the King and champion of faith, the humble beggar Muhammad Tahir . . . Uddin Husain, son of Sultān 'Alī Sabzwārī was successful in erecting this noble building in the month of Muḥarram of the year 1014 (Muḥarram of 1014 A.H. began on the 9th May 1605 A.D.)”

BĀZ BAHĀDUR KA MAḤALL.

Near Riwā Kund there is a palace built by Nāṣiruddīn said to have been repaired by Bāz Bahādur and locally known as “Bāz Bahādur kā Maḥall.” The entrance arch bears the following inscription of which no rubbing could be taken and which has been read on the stone :—

XVIII.

بزمان . . . السلطان الاعدل الاعظم الخاقان العلم الاكرم ناصر شاه . . . كته يوسف
سنه ٩١٤ هجرى

“During the time of . . . the Sultān the just and great, the learned and noble Khāqān . . . written by Yūsuf in the year 914 (1508—9 A.D.)”

TĀL MASJID.

There is an Arabic inscription on Tāl-Masjid at Dharam Purī measuring 14½” by 9½” and containing a well-known Hadīth often quoted in Indian inscriptions.

XIX.

قال رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم - من بني مسجد الله بني الله له قصر في الجنة
عامره شيخ إدراك سنه ٩١٠ هجرى

“The prophet, God’s peace and blessing be with him, said, ‘who builds a mosque for God God builds for him a palace in paradise.’

Built by Shaikh Idrāk in 910 (1504—5 A.D.)”

MOSQUE NEAR DELHI GATE.

The following inscription (see Plate X. No. 1) measuring 22½” by 20½” is found on the doorway of a ruined mosque near the Delhi gate.

XX.

الملك دهار . . . مسجد . . .
اعلى خان كبير . . . ضابط مسند على حسام الدنيا والدين اعظم همايون
المخاطب شاه عالم . . . كنه . . . قته . . .
ا . . . تاريخ . . . من ربيع الاخر سنه
عشرين . . .

“ . . . the king, Dhār . . . mosque . . . the exalted and great Khān
 . . . the occupant of the high throne, the sword of the world and
 religion (Ḥusāmu-d-dunyā wad-dīn) A‘zam Humāyūn . . . styled Shāh ‘Ālām, . . .
 . . . Rabi‘ul Ākhir the year . . . 20.¹”

RŪPMATĪ QĤHATRĪ.

At a short distance from Riwā Kund, there is Rūpmatī Qhatri (a small ornamental pavilion). It bears an inscription engraved on a black stone slab measuring 36" by 20" in small sunk letters. The inscription has been very badly damaged and the rubbing proved unsatisfactory. I could read the following words from the stone.

XXI.

بنا . . . ظل الله . . . ردهار . . .
 . . . خان . . . سيد . . . عاجز ما . . .
 . . . جرد . . . خانقاه حضر . . . سيد . . .
 . . . جماعتخان ا . . .

This inscription seems to refer to a Khānqāh and one Jamā‘at Khān is mentioned in connection with it.

NIL KANṬH.

In a valley towards west there is a building called Nil Kanṭh which at present serves as a Hindū temple. Literally Nil Kanṭh means "blue necked," and there is an Indian bird of that quality (*Coracias indica*) that is held sacred by the Hindūs. There are five inscriptions found in it.

(a) Over the big northern outer arch. This inscription (see Plate XIV) is written in one line, 31" by 11½". The stone slabs on which the inscription is written have been wrongly put together by some illiterate restorer. The plate is the reproduction of the rubbing in which the text has been arranged in the correct order.

XXII.

امر بنای هذا العمارت الدلكشا بعهد السلطان الاعظم الخاقان العدل والاكرم مرلی ملك
 العرب والعجم ظل الله في الارضين قهرمان [ا] لمام والطین وافع رايات المجاهدات والمغازی
 ابوالفتح جلال الدين محمد اكبر بادشاه غازي خلد الله ملكه و سلطانه كتبه فریدرن حسین ابن
 حاتمی . سنه ۹۸۲ هجری

"This pleasant building was ordered to be built in the reign of the great Sultān, the most merciful and just Khāqān, the lord of the kings of 'Arab and 'Ajam, the shadow of God on the two earths, the ruler of the sea and of the land, who raises the standards of holy wars and campaigns, Abul Faṭḥ Jalāluddīn Muḥammad Akbar, the king Champion of faith; may God make his dominion and kingdom last for ever! Written by Farīdūn Ḥusain, son of Ḥātīmī . the year 982 (1574-5 A.D.)"

¹ A‘zam Humāyūn reigned from 917—88. Most probably, therefore, the last portion of the date, which is illegible, is تسعمائة (nine hundred).

(b) On the northern inner arch.¹ This inscription is quoted in *Maāthir-al-umarā* (Bibl. Ind.) Vol. II, p. 537, where also a biography of *Shāh Budāgh Khān* is to be found.

XXIII.

توان کردن تمامی عمر را مصروف آب و گل
که شاید یکدمی صاحب دل اینجا کند منزل
کتبه شاه بداغ خان سنه ۹۸۲ هجری

"The whole life may be spent in water and earth (i.e. in building,) as possibly a man of piety may choose this place as his lodging for a moment.

Written by *Shāh Budāgh Khān*, the year 982 Hijra (1574-5 A.D.)."

(c) On the right wing of the outer arch. The inscription (see Plate XVI) measures 41" by 21".

XXIV.

در تاریخ سنه ۴۴ الهی موافق سنه ۱۰۰۸ بندگان اعلیحضرت جهان پناه فلک بارگاه ظل الله
متوجه فتح دکن بردند بدینجا عبور افتاد

(۱) تا کے گوی بچرخ شد خانه ما خذند همه بر دل دیوانه ما
(۲) ز افسانه دیگران بیا عبرت گیر زان پیش که بشنوند افسانه ما

"In the 44th year of the divine era corresponding to 1008 (1599—1600 A.D.) the slaves of His Exalted Majesty, the protection of the world, whose court is like the sky, the shadow of God passed by this place on their way to the conquest of the Deccan.

(1) How long wilt thou say "our house is raised to heaven" ? All the people laughed at our vain heart.

(2) Come and derive a lesson from the story of others before they hear our story."

On the left hand side of the outer arch two inscriptions are found, viz., (d) and (e) (see Plate XV.)

(d) The inscription measures 25½" by 18½".

XXV.

حضرت ظل الله اکبر بادشاه فتح دکن ر داندیس نموده در سنه ۱۰۰۹ عازم هند شدند
قائله نامی

(۱) دیدم چغله نشسته در صبح یگانه برکنگره مقبره شرزان شاه
(۲): فریاد کنان ز روی عبرت میگفت کو آن همه حشمت کجا آن همه جاه

¹ It was impossible to take the rubbing from the stone on account of there being near it a bee-hive with which some local superstition is connected.

"His Majesty, the shadow of God, the king Akbar after having conquered the Deccan and Dāndes¹ set out for Hind in the year 1009 (1600-1 A.D.); composed by Nāmī.

(1) At dawn I saw an owl sitting on the pinnacle of Shīrwān Shāh's tomb.

(2) Plaintively it uttered the warning, 'Where is all that glory and where all that splendour?'"

(e) The inscription measures 26" by 8½".

XXVI.

بتاریخ سنه ۱۰۰۹ حضرت اکبر بادشاه فتح داندیس ر دکن نمرده عازم هند شدند

حرر محمد معصوم

"In the year 1009 (1600-1 A.D.) His Majesty the king Akbar after making the conquest of Dāndes and the Deccan set out for Hind. Written by Muḥammad Ma'ṣūm.²"

BADR SHĀH.

The locality known as Badr Shāh contains a few tombs and the ruins of a building. One of these tombs has verses written on its four sides (see Plate XVIII).

(a) The inscription measures 11½" by 5".

XXVII.

چشم انست که ز شوق تو نهد سر بلعد

تادم صبح قیامت نگران خواهد بود

"The eye (of the man of insight) for the sake of thy love lays the head on the grave; it will be watching till the morn of the day of resurrection."

(b) The inscription measures 12" x 5".

بر سر تربت من چون گفری همت خواه

که زیارت که رندان جهان خواهد بود

"When you pass by my grave implore (God's) favour, as it will be the place of pilgrimage for the Sufis of the world."

(c) The inscription measures 17" by 5½".

خود رفته ایم در کنج مزاریه گرفته ایم

"We have gone ourselves, and taken abode in the corner of a grave."

¹ "This flourishing country was called Khāndes, but after the capture of the fortress of Asir (1008) and when this province fell under the government of prince Dāmpāl, it was known as Dāndēs." *Asir Akbari*, English translation by Jarret, Vol. II, p. 222.

² Muḥammad Ma'ṣūm is the same as Nāmī, "e" corresponds exactly to the first half of "(d)" except for the order of words. It is difficult to say why this inscription should have been written twice. Possibly it was intended by Nāmī to add some verses in "e."

(d) The inscription measures 17" by 5½".

تا بار دوش کس نشود استخوان ما

"Lest our bones should be a burden on any one's shoulder."

Among the rubbings in the collection of estampages belonging to the Dhār State, there is one which according to the list attached has been taken from an inscription in Badr Shāh. This inscription was not any more to be found when I visited Māndū in the year 1910. It may have been removed to some other place as has been the case with inscription No. XXX. Under the Persian text there are a few lines in Sanskrit, which various Sanskrit scholars declared to be unreadable. The whole of it (see Plate XIII) measures 26½" by 14½".

XXVIII.

از پیش بندگی سلطان السلاطین امام الدنیا والدین مدالله جلاله شهنه ر . . . ر پتواری
 رعایا قصبه . . . ارزا عمال شنا . . . شهر شادیاباد متصرف دانند بیست بیگمه
 زمین . . . کانیدن چاه و نصب کردن باغ در . . . اولاد و احفاد گریال بارس
 بن . . . رسانید ماه . . . استقبال شهر سنه سبع و ثمانمایه
 تعمیر گردانیده شده است باید که زمین مذکور سال بسال . . . اند . . . اند

"From the august presence of the Sultān of Sultāns, the head in the secular and religious affairs may God increase his glory! The peon . . . the paṭwārī and the ryot of the village . . . should know him to be tax collector . . . of the city of Shādiābād. Twenty bigās of land . . . digging up a well and planting a garden in it . . . the progeny and descendants of Gopāl Bāras, son of . . . month . . . months of the year 807 (1404-5 A.D.) has been built. The aforesaid land should be every year"

TOMB OF MALĀḤAT DĀI.

On the tomb of Malāḥat Dāi. The inscription (see Plate X. No. 2) measures 25" by 12".

XXIX.

هو الله

چارشنبه یازدهم ربیع الثانی هزار و صد و هشت راقعة دده ملامت شد

"He is God.

On Wednesday, the 11th of Rabi' the second in 1108 (28th Oct. 1696 A.D.) the nurse Malāḥat died."

NĀLQHA.

The following inscription is written on a broken piece of marble in Tughrā characters, and is not complete (see Plate XII. No. 2). It is said to have been brought from Nālqha and is

now placed in the State High school, Dhār. As the letters are rather indistinct, I am not sure that my reading is correct.

XXX.

- | | | |
|--|--|-----|
| روزان احمد مرسل که شان ارست دررد | سپاس رشکر خدا را که برگزیده فضل ¹ | (۱) |
| ابوالمظفر خلجی نصب ² شه محمود | بعهد خسرو جمشید فر علی سیرت | (۲) |
| که ار بعرض سرلمعه . بذر . غنود | بعهد خدارند نجم مهد نظام | (۳) |
| ردای درش ا . . . مملکت افزود | . . . جهان کرم ملک . . . | (۴) |
| مڈال ررضه بکردش که هیچ کس نشنود | [۵] سصد ر پنجاه ر یک هجرت . . . | (۵) |

(1) "Thanks to God that He selected with His grace the soul of Ahmad the prophet, whose lofty position is worthy of praises and benedictions.

(2) During the reign of the king combining the glory of Jamsbed and disposition of 'Ali, Abul Muza'far Shāh Mahmūd of the Khiljī dynasty ;

(3) . . . during the reign of the lord of administration, whose cradle is among the stars ; and who

(4) the cloak of shoulders increased kingdom.

(5) 851 Hijra (1447-8 A.D.) built it like a rauza (of the equal of which) no one has ever heard."

¹ بفضل gives no meaning here. It should be بفضل.

² I am not sure whether this word is نصب or نصیب. According to the context it means نصب